

On Square Difference Graphs

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Abstract: In graph theory number labeling problems play vital role. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a (p, q) -graph with vertex set V and edge set E . Let f be a vertex valued bijective function from $V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$. An edge valued function f^* can be defined on G as a function of squares of vertex values. Graphs which satisfy the injectivity of this type of edge valued functions are called square graphs. Square graphs have two major divisions: they are square sum graphs and square difference graphs. In this paper we concentrate on square difference or SD graphs. An edge labeling f^* on $E(G)$ can be defined as follows. $f^*(uv) = |(f(u))^2 - (f(v))^2|$ for every uv in $E(G)$. If f^* is injective, then the labeling is said to be a SD labeling. A graph which satisfies SD labeling is known as a SD graph.

We illuminate some of the results on number theory into the structure of SD graphs. Also, established some classes of SD graphs and established that every graph can be embedded into a SD graph.

Key Words: SD labeling, SD graph, strongly SD graph, perfect SD graph.

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§1. Introduction

The research in graph enumeration and graph labeling started way back in 1857 by Arthur Cayley. Graph labeling and enumeration finds the application in chemical graph theory, social networking and computer networking and channel assignment problem. Abundant literature exists as of today concerning the structure of graphs admitting a variety of functions assigning real numbers to their elements so that certain given conditions are satisfied. Here we are

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interested the study of vertex functions $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ for which an edge valued injective function f^* can be defined on G as function of squares of vertex values. Graphs which satisfy this type of labeling are called square graphs. Square graphs have two major divisions: they are square sum graphs and square difference graphs.

In this paper, we concentrate on square difference or *SD* graphs. This new type of labeling of graphs is closely related to the equation $x^2 - y^2 = n$. It is important to note that certain numbers like 6, 10, 14 etc., cannot be written as the difference of two squares. Hence it is very interesting to study those graphs which takes the first consecutive numbers that can be expressed as the difference of two squares. Here, consider only a finite undirected graph without loops or multiple edges. Terms not specifically defined in this paper may be found in Harrary (1969), [6] and all the number theoretic results used here found in [3,4] and [2,8].

Here we recall some results of number theory, which are essential for our study.

Definition 1.1 *An integer is said to be representable if it can be represent as difference of two squares.*

Theorem 1.2([7]) *The product of any number of representable integers is also representable.*

Theorem 1.3([7]) *Every square integer is of the form following*

(i) $4q$ or $4q + 1$;

(ii) $5q$, $5q + 1$ or $5q - 1$.

Theorem 1.4([7]) *If $n = x^2 - y^2$, then $n \equiv 0, 1, 3 \pmod{4}$.*

Corollary 1.5([7]) *An odd number is a difference of two successive squares.*

Theorem 1.6([7]) *The difference of squares of consecutive numbers is equal to the sum of the numbers.*

§2. SD Graphs

Definition 2.1 *Let $G = (V, E)$ be a (p, q) -graph with vertex set V and edge set E . Let f be a vertex valued bijective function from $V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$. An edge valued function f^* can be defined on G as $f^*(uv) = |(f(u))^2 - (f(v))^2|$ for every uv in $E(G)$. If f^* is injective, then the labeling is said to be a *SD* labeling. A graph which satisfies *SD* labeling is known as an *SD* graph.*

Example 2.2 An example of *SD* graphs is given below.

Fig.1

The following are some simple observations obtained immediately from the definition of *SD* graph.

Observation 2.3 For every edge $e = uv \in E(G)$ then $f^*(e) \equiv 0, 1, 3 \pmod{4}$.

Observation 2.4 If $e = uv \in E(G)$ with $f(u) = 0$ then $f^*(e) \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4}$.

Observation 2.5 For a *SD* graph the product of edge values is a representable number.

Observation 2.6 Let G be a (p, q) -graph with a square difference labeling f then $[f(u)]^2$ occurs $d(u)$ times in the sum $\sum f^*(e)$. Take the p vertices of G as u_1, u_2, \dots, u_p and assign values to them in such a way that $f(u_1) < f(u_2) < \dots < f(u_p)$, then for all $i = 0, 1, \dots, p - 1$ we have

$$\sum f^*(e) = d(u_p) [f(u_p)]^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} (k_i - l_i) [f(u_i)]^2, \text{ where for each edge } u_i u_j,$$

$k_i =$ number of vertices u_j with $f(u_i) > f(u_j), i \neq j$

$l_i =$ number of vertices u_j with $f(u_i) < f(u_j), i \neq j$

In particular if $k_i = l_i$ for all i , we get the above result as $\sum f^*(e) = d(u_p) [f(u_p)]^2$.

Theorem 2.7 Let G be a connected *SD* graph with an *SD* labeling f . Then $f^*(e) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ for at least one edge $e \in E(G)$. Further if $f^*(e) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \forall e \in E(G)$, then G is bipartite.

Proof Let $X = \{u : f(u) \text{ is even}\}$ and $Y = \{v : f(v) \text{ is odd}\}$. Since G is connected there exists at least one edge $e = uv$ such that $u \in X$ and $v \in Y$. Hence $f^*(e) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. If $f^*(e) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \forall e \in E(G)$, it follows that $f(u)$ and $f(v)$ are of opposite parity and X and Y form a bipartition of G and G is a bipartite graph. \square

§3. Some classes of *SD* graphs

Theorem 3.1 The graph $G = K_2 + mK_1$ is an *SD* graph.

Proof Let $V(G) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{m+2}\}$ where $V(K_2) = \{u_1, u_2\}$. Define $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, m + 1\}$ by $f(u_i) = i - 1, 1 \leq i \leq m + 2$. Clearly, the induced function f^* is injective, for if $f^*(u_1 u_i) = f^*(u_2 u_j)$ then, $|[f(u_1)]^2 - [f(u_i)]^2| = |[f(u_2)]^2 - [f(u_j)]^2|$. Since $f(u_1) = 0$ and $f(u_2) = 1$, we get $(f(u_i))^2 = (f(u_j))^2 - 1$ so that either $f(u_i) = 0$ or $f(u_j) = 0$, which is a contradiction. Hence f^* is injective and G is an *SD* graph. \square

Theorem 3.2 *Every star is an SD graph.*

Proof Let $V(K_{1,n}) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, u_{n+1}\}$ where $e_i = u_1u_i$ for $2 \leq i \leq n$. Define $f : V(K_{1n}) \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, n - 1\}$ as $f(u_1) = 0$ and $f(u_i) = i - 1$. Then $f^*(E(K_{1,n})) = \{1^2, 2^2, \dots, (n - 1)^2\}$ and hence f^* is infective and f is a *SD* labeling on K_{1n} . Hence every star is an *SD* graph. \square

Theorem 3.3 *Every path is an SD graph.*

Proof Let $P_n = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n)$ where $e_i = u_iu_{i+1}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Define $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, n - 1\}$ as $f(u_i) = i - 1$. Then by the Theorem ?? $f^*(E(P_n)) = \{1, 3, \dots, 2n - 3\}$ and hence f^* is infective and f is a *SD* labeling on P_n . Hence every path is an *SD* graph. \square

Theorem 3.4 *A complete graph K_n is SD if and only if $n \leq 5$.*

Proof The *SD* labeling of the complete graph K_n for $n \leq 5$ is given in figures 2 and 5. Further since $5^2 - 4^2 = 3^2 - 0^2$ it follows that $K_n, n \geq 6$ is not an *SD* graph. \square

Fig.2

Fig.3

Theorem 3.5 *Every cycle is an SD graph.*

Proof Let $C_n = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n)$ where $e_i = u_iu_{i+1}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n - 1$ and $e_n = u_nu_1$. Define $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, n - 1\}$ as $f(u_i) = i - 1$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Also $f^*(E(C_n)) = \{1, 3, \dots, 2n - 3, (n - 1)^2\}$. If n is odd then $(n - 1)^2$ is even, so f^* is infective and f is a *SD* labeling on C_n . If n is even, since $(n - 1)^2 > 2n - 3$ for $n \geq 3$, then also f^* is injective and f is a *SD* labeling on C_n . Hence cycles are *SD* graphs. \square

Theorem 3.6 Every friendship graph $C_3^{(n)}$ is an SD graph.

Proof Let G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n be the n copies of C_3 , all concatenated at exactly one vertex say, z . Let $G_i = (z, u_{i1}, u_{i2}), 1 \leq i \leq n$. Define $f : V(C_3^{(n)}) \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, 2n\}$ as $f(z) = 0, f(u_{i1}) = i$ and $f(u_{i2}) = n + i$. Then $f^*(E(C_3^{(n)})) = \{1^2, 2^2, \dots, (2n)^2, n^2 + 2n, n^2 + 4n, n^2 + 6n, \dots, 3n^2\}$ and the induced edge function f^* is injective and f is an SD labeling on $C_3^{(n)}$. Hence the proof. \square

Definition 3.7([1]) A cycle-cactus is such a graph that consisting of n copies of $C_k, k \geq 3$ concatenated at exactly one vertex is denoted as $C_k^{(n)}$.

Theorem 3.8 A complete bipartite graphs $K_{m,n}$ is SD if $m \leq 4$ for any integer $n \geq 1$.

Proof Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\}, Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\}$ be the partition of $K_{m,n}$. Define a vertex labeling as follows:

- (1) If $m = 1$, then $f(x_1) = 0$ and $f(y_i) = i, 1 \leq i \leq n$;
- (2) If $m = 2$, then $f(x_1) = 0, f(x_2) = 1$ and $f(y_i) = i + 1, 1 \leq i \leq n$;
- (3) If $m = 3$, then $f(x_1) = 0, f(x_2) = 1, f(x_3) = 2$ and $f(y_i) = i + 2, 1 \leq i \leq n$;
- (4) If $m = 4$, then $f(x_1) = 0, f(x_2) = 1, f(x_3) = 3, f(x_4) = 5$ and $f(y_i) = 2i$, if $i = 1, 2, 3, f(y_i) = 2i - 1$, if $i = 4$, and $f(y_i) = i + 3$, if $i > 4$.

It is easy to verify that the edge valued function f^* is injective on $E(K_{m,n})$ and hence the theorem. \square

Theorem 3.9 Every triangle snake is an SD graph.

Proof Let G be a triangle snake with $2n + 1$ vertices and let the vertex set $V(G)$ be $\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n+1}\}$ and the edge set $E(G)$ be $\{u_i v_i, u_i v_{i+1}, v_i v_{i+1}\}$, where $1 \leq i \leq n$. We can define a vertex labeling $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2n\}$ as $f(u_i) = 2i - 1, 1 \leq i \leq n$ and $f(v_i) = 2(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq n + 1$. Then the corresponding edge function f^* is injective and hence all triangle snakes are SD graphs. \square

Example 3.10 The following example gives an illustration for the above theorem.

Fig.4

Observation 3.11 P_4 is a connected SD graph with prime edge labels.

Proof A prime number is a representable number if and only if it can be represent as difference of two consecutive integers. Hence there exist a *SD* labelling on P_4 with prime edge values as follows

Fig.5

This completes the proof. □

Corollary 3.12 *A connected 5 vertexed graph with prime edge values is isomorphic to P_4 .*

Corollary 3.13 *There is not exist a connected (p, q) - *SD* graph with prime edge values if $p > 5$.*

Conjecture 3.14 *Every tree is an *SD* graph.*

Conjecture 3.15 *Every cycle-cactus $C_k^{(n)}$ is an *SD* graph.*

Conjecture 3.16 *Every complete bipartite graph is an *SD* graph.*

§4. Strongly *SD* Graphs

Definition 4.1 *An *SD* graph is said to be a strongly *SD* if the edge values are consecutive representable numbers.*

In other words, an *SD* graph $G = (V, E)$ is said to be a strongly *SD* if $f^*(E(G))$ consists the first q consecutive numbers of the form $a^2 - b^2$, $a \leq p - 1$, $b \leq p - 1$, $a \neq b$ and the corresponding labeling is said to be a strongly *SD* labeling of G .

Example 4.2 An example of a strongly *SD* graph is given below.

Fig.6

Theorem 4.3 *Every strongly *SD* graph except K_1, K_2 and $K_{1,2}$ contain at least one triangle.*

Proof Clearly K_1, K_2 and $K_{1,2}$ are triangle free strongly SD graphs. For a strongly square difference graph with three edges, the possible edge values are 1, 3 and 4. To obtain the edge value 3, the vertices which label 1 and 2 should be adjacent. Similarly to obtain the edge value 4, the vertices which label 0 and 2 should be adjacent. In this case the graph should contains a triangle (uvw) with $f(u) = 0, f(v) = 1$ and $f(w) = 2$. \square

Corollary 4.4 *All cycles $C_n, n \geq 4$ are not strongly SD graphs.*

Corollary 4.5 *A complete bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$ is a strongly SD graph if and only if $m = 1, n \leq 2$.*

Theorem 4.6 *A unicyclic graph is strongly SD if and only if it is either C_3 or C_3 with one pendant edge or C_3 with a path of length 2.*

Proof Clearly, C_3, C_3 with one pendant edge and are strongly SD graphs. Suppose G is a unicyclic graph which is strongly SD . Then $f^*(E(G)) = \{1, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, \dots\}$.

If $f^*(E(G)) = \{1, 3, 4\}$, then $G \cong C_3$;

If $f^*(E(G)) = \{1, 3, 4, 5\}$, then G is isomorphic to C_3 along with one pendant edge;

If $f^*(E(G)) = \{1, 3, 4, 5, 7\}$, then G is isomorphic to C_3 along with a path of length 2;

If $f^*(E(G)) = \{1, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8\}$, then to obtain the edge value 8, the vertices with labels 3 and 1 should be adjacent. In this case one more triangle will be formed, a contradiction since G is unicyclic.

Therefore the unicyclic graphs which admits a strongly SD labeling are either C_3 or C_3 with one pendant edge or C_3 with a path of length 2. \square

Conjecture 4.7 *Every cycle $C_n, n \geq 4$ can be embedded as an induced subgraph of a strongly SD graph.*

Problem 4.8 *Find the number of strongly SD graphs for a given number of edges.*

Problem 4.9 *Characterize the strongly SD graphs.*

By the definition of SD graphs it is clear that a big family of graphs are not SD . Hence on SD graphs embedding theorems have an important role to play. In the following section we proved an embedding theorem.

§5. Embeddings on SD Graphs

Theorem 5.1 *Every (p, q) - graph G can be embedded into a connected SD graph.*

Proof Let G be a graph with vertex set $V(G) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_p\}$. We shall establish an embedding of G in H , where H is a graph with $|V(H)| = 5^{p-1} + 1$ and $|E(H)| = 5^{p-1} + q - p$. Label the vertices of G by $f(u_1) = 0, f(u_2) = 1$ and $f(u_i) = 5^{i-1}, 3 \leq i \leq p$. Let v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the isolated vertices where $n = 5^{p-1} + 1 - p$. Let $X = \{1, 2, \dots, 5^{p-1} - 1\}$. Label the

vertices v_i with the numbers from the set $X - \{5, 5^2, \dots, 5^{p-1}\}$. The graph H obtained from G as follows. Join u_1 to v_k if $f(v_k)$ is odd for $1 \leq k \leq n$ and u_2 to v_l if $f(v_l)$ is even for $1 \leq l \leq n$. Clearly f is a bijection from $V(H) \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, 5^{p-1}\}$. Now we prove that the induced edge labeling f^* is injective. Assume $f^*(e_1) = f^*(e_2)$ for some $e_1, e_2 \in E(G)$. Since f is injective it follows that e_1 and e_2 are non adjacent. Suppose $e_1 = u_k u_l$ and $e_2 = u_i u_j$ where $1 \leq i \leq j, k \leq l \leq p$. Then $(5^j)^2 - (5^l)^2 = (5^i)^2 + (5^k)^2$ from which we obtain $(5^i)^2 + (5^k)^2 = (5^l)^2 + (5^j)^2$. If $u_i = u_1$ then $(5^k)^2 = (5^l)^2 + (5^j)^2$ which is a contradiction. Otherwise dividing both sides of the equation by $(5a)^2$, where $a = \min(i, j, k, l)$, we get an edge where one side is congruent to $1 \pmod{5}$ and the other side is congruent to $0 \pmod{5}$, which is a contradiction. If $e_1 = u_k u_l$ and $e_2 = u_1 v_i$ then $f^*(e_1) = f^*(e_2) \Rightarrow (5^l)^2 - (5^k)^2 = (f(v_i))^2$ if $f(v_i)$ is odd and $(5^l)^2 - (5^k)^2 = (f(v_i))^2 - 1$ if $f(v_i)$ is even. In both case we get contradictions. Hence the induced function f^* is a SD labeling and the graph H is a SD graph which contains G as a subgraph. \square

§6. Perfect SD Graphs

Definition 6.1 *An SD graph is said to be a perfect SD graph if the edge values are consecutive perfect squares. The corresponding SD labelling is said to be a perfect SD labelling.*

Example 6.2

Fig.7

Observation 6.3 *Every star is a perfect SD graph.*

Observation 6.4 *The cycles C_3, C_4 and C_5 are not perfect SD graphs.*

Observation 6.5 *Every friendship graph $C_3^{(n)}$ is not a perfect SD graph.*

Conjecture 6.6 *Every cycle is not a perfect SD graph.*

Theorem 6.7 *These graphs C_3, C_4 and C_5 can be embedded into perfect SD graph.*

Proof The following embeddings give the proof. \square

Fig.8 The embedding of C_3

Fig.9 The embedding of C_4

Fig.10 The embedding of C_5

Conjecture 6.8 *Every cycle can be embedded into a perfect SD graph.*

Theorem 6.9 *The friendship graph $C_3^{(n)}$ can be embedded into a perfect SD graph.*

Proof Let G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n be the n copies of C_3 , all concatenated at exactly one vertex say, z . Let $G_i = (z, u_{i1}, u_{i2}), 1 \leq i \leq n$. Define $f : V(C_3^{(n)}) \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, 2n\}$ as $f(z) = 0$, $f(u_{i1}) = 2i^2 + 2i + 1$ and $f(u_{i2}) = 2i + 1$. Introduce $2n^2 + 1$ new vertices V_k where $1 \leq k \leq 2n^2 + 1$. Join the vertex z to V_k where $k \neq 2i(i + 1), 1 \leq i \leq n$.

Then f is a perfect SD labeling on the embedded graph H and hence H is a perfect SD graph.

□

Problem 6.10 Every cycle-cactus $C_k^{(n)}$ can be embedded into a perfect SD graph.

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